

Photocatalytic reaction and degradation of methylene blue on TiO₂ nanosized particles

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Abstract

Photocatalyst has been of considerable interest due to its new technology for environmental pollution. Among the photocatalyst semiconductors, titanium dioxide is known as a photo-catalyst for the removal of environmental contaminants. In this research, we first designed a new self-made laboratory photocatalytic reactor and then photocatalytic properties of TiO₂ nanoparticles are studied by using UV-A light and photodegradation of methylene blue as a water pollutant evaluated until the photocatalytic process optimizes with the process parameters. The parameters that were examined include: initial dye concentration, the mass of TiO₂ nanoparticle, pH value, and TiO₂ nano-sized particles. Absorbance spectra were measured using a spectrophotometer and the concentration of the test solution was calculated by using the Beer-Lambert Law. Our test results showed that the photocatalytic UV-A/TiO₂ nanoparticle is a promising method for treating wastewater. The most important part is that with reduction of TiO₂ particles from nano to micro scale, photodegradation time becomes very slowly and even did not reach to zero after 5 h. Also, photocatalyst reaction efficiency for 10 nm TiO₂ nanoparticles improves to 90% within one hour and photodegradation completed after two hours, it means that the photocatalyst activity increases with increasing surface area.

Keywords: Photocatalyst, TiO₂ nanoparticles, Degradation, Methylene blue, Ultraviolet

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